

Supporting Information

Synergistic Enhancement of Supercapacitors with Cobalt-Copper Bimetal– Organic Framework

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Figure S1. EDS of the CoCu-MOF material

Figure S2. Optical image of Co-MOF(a), CoCu(10)-MOF(b), CoCu(6)-MOF(c) and CoCu(4)-MOF(d)

Table S1. The percentages of Cu^{2+} and Cu^+ for Cu-MOF and CoCu-MOF

	Cu^+	Cu^{2+}
Cu-MOF	82%	18%
CoCu-MOF	17%	83%